

COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE INFLUENCE OF UNSTEADY AND UNIFORM MICRO TIP INJECTIONS ON THE STABILITY OF A LOW-SPEED COMPRESSOR

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ABSTRACT

Micro tip injection effectively improves stall margin with minimal efficiency loss. This study compares uniform and unsteady micro tip injections in a low-speed compressor to reveal their effects on compressor stability. Numerical simulations were performed on a 1/10th annular sector model. Both injection methods have identical time-averaged mass flow, 0.005% of compressor's design flow per actuator. The unsteady micro tip injection (BPMI) operates at the blade passing frequency using square waves, with each actuator featuring two outlets in opposite phase, whereas the uniform injection (UI) employs a steady single outlet. The resulting flow fields are analyzed using dynamic mode decomposition (DMD). Results show that BPMI improves stall margin by 1.31%, outperforming the 0.71% achieved by UI. Due to the minimal momentum input of both schemes, their impact on the radial load distribution is negligible. DMD reveals that spillage vortex (SPV) dynamics dominate tip flow instability: The cross-passage propagation of SPV enhances leading-edge spillage and induces tornado vortex formation, marking stall onset. UI injection mitigates SPV by enhancing mid-chord leakage, wall shear, and circumferential transport, thereby improving compressor stall margin, which is a feature common to both injection schemes. The critical blockage coefficient at stall onset remains unchanged for either method. Due to its periodic nature, BPMI further concentrates leakage enhancement and amplifies leakage fluctuations, more effectively constraining SPV growth and enhancing stability.

Keywords: Unsteady aerodynamics; compressor stall; flow control; dynamic mode decomposition.

NOMENCLATURE

Place nomenclature section, if needed, here. Nomenclature should be given in a column, like this:

φ	Flow coefficient
ψ	Total-to-static pressure rise coefficient

η_{ad}	Adiabatic efficiency
C_{ax}	Axial chord length of rotor blade tip
T	The blade passage passing time
f_g	Spillage vortex generation frequency
f_s	Spillage vortex shedding frequency
BS	Baseline
UI	Uniform injection
BPMI	Injection at blade passing frequency
R1	Rotor blade 1
R2	Rotor blade 2
FP1	Flow passage 1
FP2	Flow passage 2
SPV	Spillage vortex
SMI	Stall margin improvement
DMD	Dynamic mode decomposition

1. INTRODUCTION

Modern high-performance compressors encounter increasingly severe flow instability issues while pursuing high load and high pressure ratios. Although traditional casing treatments can significantly improve stall margins, they greatly change the casing structure and may lead to considerable efficiency losses, causing difficulties in practical application [1]. Therefore, novel control methods, such as foam metal casing treatments [2] and micro tip injection [3], have started to be studied to alleviate this problem.

The total momentum input from micro tip injection is significantly smaller than the mainstream momentum. Under both low-speed and high-speed compressor conditions [4], uniform and distorted inlet conditions [5], and in both single-stage and multi-stage environments [6][7], micro tip injection can extend the compressor stall margin with minimal efficiency loss. Depending on whether the injection varies with time, it can be classified as unsteady or uniform micro tip injection. Studies [8][9] have shown that, for achieving the same level of stall margin enhancement, unsteady micro tip injection requires

a lower total injection mass compared to steady injection. When the excitation intensity is the same, unsteady micro tip injection generally yields better performance than its steady counterpart [10][11]. Therefore, to develop efficient and low-loss flow control strategies, it is crucial to clarify the differences between unsteady and uniform micro tip injections in their effects on compressor stability.

Commonly used flow field analysis methods such as direct time-domain analysis and spectral analysis can only extract localized spatial-temporal information, making it difficult to comprehensively reveal the effects of unsteady and uniform micro tip injections on the flow field. The dynamic mode decomposition (DMD) method [12] based on singular value decomposition, reduces the order of the flow field, allowing for the precise extraction of dominant flow modes and their temporal evolution. This method has been applied in studying compressor stall processes [13][14] and stability control methods [15].

In this paper, unsteady numerical simulations are conducted on a low-speed compressor. The dynamic mode decomposition (DMD) method is employed to compare the flow field under unsteady and uniform micro tip injections with identical time-averaged momentum input, aiming to highlight their differing impacts on compressor stability. This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides a brief overview of the research subject and methodology. Section 3 presents and discusses the numerical results for both unsteady and uniform micro tip injections. Finally, the main conclusions are summarized in Section 4.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Research subjects and case setups

The research object is a low-speed single-stage axial flow compressor[2], with the main design parameters shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1: THE MAIN DESIGN PARAMETER OF THE LOW-SPEED COMPRESSOR

	Rotor	Stator
Blade number	20	27
Tip radius/mm	300	300
Hub-to-tip ratio	0.577	0.669
Aspect ratio	1.18	1.40
Design operating speed/rpm	2930	
Design pressure ratio	1.0267	
Efficiency at design points/%	88	

The unsteady micro tip injection used in this study is characterized by each actuator having two outlets that emit jets of equal amplitude but opposite phase, alternating at a specified frequency. Previous experimental studies [16] have shown that this type of unsteady injection can extend the stall margin of the compressor. The unsteady injection, denoted as BPF1, is applied at the rotor blade passing frequency of 980 Hz. Injection parameters align with the experimental setup, with the

actuators positioned 0.5 times of the axial chord length (C_{ax}) downstream of the rotor blade tip leading edge. Thirty actuators are evenly distributed around the circumference, and the injection flow rate of each is 0.005% of the compressor's design flow rate. For comparison, a uniform micro tip injection (UI) case with the same time-averaged flow rate is also included to evaluate the effects of different excitation strategies on stability.

2.2 Numerical method

The numerical simulations are performed using the ANSYS CFX solver with the $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model, employing a second-order upwind scheme and an implicit time-marching method to solve the three-dimensional compressible Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes equations. For unsteady simulations, the physical time step is set to 3.41×10^{-5} s, which is 1/30 of the blade passage passing time T.

To investigate the effects of unsteady and uniform micro tip injections on compressor stability, numerical simulations are conducted using a reduced 1/10 annular sector domain, as shown in Figure 1. The inlet of the computational domain is located one rotor radius upstream of the rotor leading edge, while the outlet is positioned two stator chord length downstream of the stator outlet. In unsteady simulations, the interfaces between the rotating and stationary domains are treated with the transient rotor stator method. The inlet boundary conditions include total temperature, total pressure, and axial inflow, while the outlet boundary condition is specified as the radially balanced average static pressure. Throttling processes are simulated by gradually increasing the outlet static pressure. No-slip and adiabatic conditions are imposed on all solid walls.

FIGURE 1: THE COMPUTATIONAL DOMAIN

The actuators are modeled as mass flow inlets. For the unsteady injection, the injection is simplified to a square wave. The two outlets of each actuator have identical excitation frequency and amplitude but opposite phase, with a duty cycle of 50%. For the uniform injection, only Inject 2 in Figure 1 is activated, with a mass flow rate equal to the time-averaged flow rate of the unsteady injection. Figure 2 illustrates the mass flow

profiles for both unsteady and uniform injection cases. For the baseline condition, both outlets are set as wall, while all other settings remain unchanged. The actuators are connected to the rotor domain through a thin transition region, with fully matched grids employed at the interface.

FIGURE 2: THE MASS FLOW PROFILES OF THE UNSTEADY AND UNIFORM MICRO TIP INJECTIONS

The mesh of the compressor is generated by NUMECA Autogrid5 and is a multi-block structured grid of O4H. O-type blocks with high resolution are applied near the blade surfaces to accurately capture the viscous boundary layer, while the remaining flow domain is filled with H-type blocks. The mesh of the transition region is generated by ANSYS ICEM and is an unstructured shell/surface grid. Two mass flow inlets are defined on its upper surface based on the actual size of the experiment, with local mesh refinement applied in this area. The first layer of grids is set as $3\ \mu\text{m}$ to ensure that y^+ is less than 3.

The grid independence verification is conducted using four meshes, as shown in Table 2. The densities of four meshes are 0.30 million, 0.71 million, 0.99 million and 1.20 million. Figure 3 illustrates the variation of adiabatic efficiency (η_{ad}) and total-to-static pressure rise coefficient (ψ) with mesh density under the same flow coefficient (ϕ), which corresponds to a near-stall condition. The η_{ad} and ψ values of Grid B are almost identical to those obtained with finer meshes. Therefore, to balance computational efficiency and accuracy, Grid B is selected for subsequent calculations. The total grid number of the full computational domain, as shown in Figure 1, is 2.03 million.

TABLE 2: THE GRID DENSITIES OF FOUR MESHES

	Grid A	Grid B	Grid C	Grid D
Grid density/million	0.30	0.71	0.99	1.20

FIGURE 3: THE GRID INDEPENDENCE VERIFICATION

The computational consumption of unsteady simulation is enormous, it is necessary to identify a suitable time step to balance the computational accuracy and cost. Therefore, a physical time step independence verification is carried out. Figure 4 compares the results of unsteady calculations at different time step. The horizontal axis represents the number of time steps per blade passage. When the number of time steps is 30 or more, the fan performance remains essentially unchanged. This indicates that the chosen time step size is appropriate for this study.

FIGURE 4: THE TIME STEP INDEPENDENCE VERIFICATION

Based on the computational domain shown in Figure 1, steady simulations are carried out for the baseline (BS) to verify the accuracy of the computational setup. Figure 5 shows the comparison of the calculated and experimental results. The calculated pressure rise characteristics for the baseline show good agreement with the experimental trend. The deviation of the flow coefficient at the near-stall point between the simulation and experiment is only 1.94%, and the deviation in the total-to-static pressure rise coefficient is just 0.18%. Meanwhile, as shown in Figure 5(b), the radial distribution of the stator outlet total pressure ratio during throttling is also in good agreement with the experiment, with a maximum deviation of less than 0.39%. Therefore, the numerical results

match the experimental data well, indicating that the results obtained using this mesh and computational setup are highly accurate.

(1) THE PRESSURE RISE CHARACTERISTIC

(2) THE TOTAL PRESSURE RATIO DISTRIBUTION OF STATOR OUTLET

FIGURE 5: THE CALCULATION ACCURACY VERIFICATION

2.3 Dynamic mode decomposition method

The exact DMD method proposed by Tu et al. [17] is used to extract characteristic modes of the flow field. After unsteady CFD simulations converge, transient flow fields are collected at equal time intervals to obtain time-resolved snapshots and form a time series. The X and Y matrices are defined as follows:

$$X = [z_0, z_1, \dots, z_{m-1}] \quad (1)$$

$$Y = [z_1, z_2, \dots, z_m] \quad (2)$$

The matrix X is decomposed using singular value decomposition:

$$X = U\Sigma V^* \quad (3)$$

The Koopman operator \tilde{A} is defined as:

$$\tilde{A} = U^*YV\Sigma^{-1} \quad (4)$$

The eigenvalues and eigenvectors of the matrix \tilde{A} are computed, and each non-zero eigenvalue is taken as a DMD eigenvalue:

$$\tilde{A}W = W\Lambda \quad (5)$$

The DMD modes are calculated using the method proposed by Brunton et al. [18]:

$$\Phi = YV\Sigma^{-1}W \quad (6)$$

Let the column vectors of Φ be $\phi_1, \dots, \phi_{m-1}$; each of which represents a dynamic mode associated with the flow field.

The initial flow field snapshot is projected onto the DMD modes, where B represents the amplitudes of the DMD modes.

$$z_0 = \Phi B \quad (7)$$

Then the flow field at any given time can be reconstructed in the following form:

$$z_{i+1,rec} = \Phi \Lambda^i B \quad (8)$$

By expressing each mode separately, the reconstructed flow field can also be written in the following form:

$$z_{i+1,rec} = \sum_{k=1}^r \lambda_k^i b_k \phi_k \quad (9)$$

Here, r represents the rank of the matrix. In the process of flow field analysis, the coherent structures associated with specific characteristic frequencies can be obtained by reconstructing the corresponding DMD modes over time.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Overall Performance

To accurately capture the stall boundary, unsteady simulations start from the flow coefficient corresponding to the stable boundary obtained by the baseline calculation ($\varphi = 0.1981$). The outlet static pressure is gradually increased by 2 Pa for both with and without injection conditions until the stable results and the complete stall development process are obtained.

Figure 6 presents the overall calculated pressure rise characteristics for the BS, BPFJ injection, and UI injection cases, along with the last calculated near-stall point for each. The results show that both BPFJ and UI injection can extend the stall margin without altering the compressor's original pressure rise characteristics, and there are differences between the two in the improvement range. The stall margin

improvement (SMI) is defined in Equation (10), the SMI of BPFi is 1.31%, and the SMI of UI is 0.71%.

$$SMI = \frac{\varphi_{BS, stall} - \varphi_{Injection, stall}}{\varphi_{BS, stall}} \times 100\% \quad (10)$$

FIGURE 6: THE CALCULATED PRESSURE RISE CHARACTERISTICS

When $\varphi = 0.1981$, Figure 7 compares the radial distributions of the time-averaged diffusion factor for BS and the two injection cases. At the same flow coefficient, the time-averaged blade loading resulting from the two injection strategies is nearly identical, with a difference of less than 0.06%. Since the total energy input of the two jet schemes is the same and small compared to the mainstream, both BPFi and UI injections barely change the radial distribution of the diffusion factor compared to BS. This indicates that the superior SMI provided by BPFi is primarily attributed to its unsteady characteristics.

FIGURE 7: $\varphi = 0.1981$, THE RADIAL DISTRIBUTION OF THE TIME-AVERAGED DIFFUSION FACTOR

3.2 Flow field analysis of the baseline

In this section, the near-stall and stall process of BS are analyzed to elucidate the key factors leading to stall onset.

In near-stall conditions, the main feature of the BS flow field in the tip region is the periodic generation and shedding of the spillage vortex (SPV). Taking $\varphi = 0.1981$ as an example, a DMD analysis is carried out at the 99% rotor span static pressure field. As shown in Fig. 8(1), the DMD frequency spectrum shows that the first two dominant frequencies are 0.679 BPF and 1.358 BPF, corresponding to the SPV generation frequency and its second harmonic. The SPV generation frequency is denoted as f_g and marked in orange. Figure 8(2) first presents instantaneous vortex core distributions in the rotor tip region. The two rotor blades are denoted as R1 and R2. The SPV is outlined in red, originating at the leading edge on the pressure side. It is induced by the combined effects of the leading edge spillage and tip leakage flow from the upstream blade, promoting the leading edge spillage, as R1 at 0/30T. The time interval between two SPV generations at the leading edge is 44/30T, which is consistent with f_g . As indicated by the blue dashed arrow, the generated SPV convects downstream and sheds near the trailing edge. The SPV shedding cycle is 2T, corresponding to a frequency of 0.5 BPF, which is identified as the fifth dominant mode in the flow field and denoted as f_s , marked in blue in Fig. 8(1). Figure 8(2) also presents the reconstructed flow fields of the SPV generation and shedding modes in terms of static pressure coefficient C_{ps} , corresponding to the vortex core distribution. The definition of C_{ps} is shown in Equation (11), where p represents the local static pressure, p_{atm} represents the atmosphere pressure, and U_m represents the mid-span circumferential velocity of the rotor blade. The phase of the SPV generation mode is almost opposite in the two channels, while the phase difference of the shedding mode is small in the two channels.

$$C_{ps} = \frac{p - p_{atm}}{0.5\rho U_m^2} \quad (11)$$

(1) DMD FREQUENCY SPECTRUM

(2) INSTANTANEOUS VORTEX CORE DISTRIBUTION AND THE RECONSTRUCTED FLOW FIELD OF f_g AND f_s

FIGURE 8: $\varphi = 0.1981$, DMD ANALYSIS RESULTS AND INSTANTANEOUS VORTEX CORE DISTRIBUTION ($Q = 1.06 \times 10^6$)

To quantify the factors influencing SPV generation and the effects of its shedding process within the passage, define leading-edge spillage intensity (Spillage) and blockage coefficient (Blockage) in the passage. Figure 9 shows the contour of static entropy at 0.99 blade height, the two flow passages are denoted as FP1 and FP2. The leading-edge spillage intensity is characterized by the distance l_s between the rotor inlet and the isosurface [19], where the static entropy is $-30 \text{ J}/(\text{kg}\cdot\text{K})$, at 4% of the pitch width from the pressure side. This is non-dimensionalized by the axial chord length C_{ax} at the rotor tip, as shown in Equation (12). The influence of SPV shedding on the passage is evaluated by the blockage coefficient [20], as defined in Equation (13). In this equation, A_t denotes the passage area, subscript d denotes the velocity deficit region; z represents the axial direction, e denotes the velocity deficit boundary, and 1 refers to the rotor inlet.

$$\text{Spillage} = \frac{l_s}{C_{ax}} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{Blockage} = \frac{1}{A_t} \int_d \left(1 - \frac{\rho_d v_{z,d}}{\rho_e v_{z,1}}\right) dA \times 100\% \quad (13)$$

FIGURE 9: QUANTIFICATION METHOD OF THE LEADING EDGE SPIILAGE

Figure 10 illustrates the evolution of the Spillage and the Blockage at $0.5 C_{ax}$ during the throttling process, along with snapshots of instantaneous vortex core distributions ($Q = 1.06 \times 10^6$). $\varphi = 0.2050$ and $\varphi = 0.1981$ represent stable near-stall conditions. The figure presents the fluctuation of Blockage and Spillage within a single rotor revolution. The stall process is initiated by increasing the outlet pressure by 2 Pa from condition $\varphi = 0.1981$. As throttling, the leading-edge spillage intensifies, and the SPV expands in blade passages, manifested by an increase in Blockage. During stall process, SPV continues to strengthen. From the moment indicated by the blue dashed line in Figure 10, SPV expands to across the entire blade passage, causing a rapid and sustained rise in Blockage. This rapid increase in Blockage reduces the passage's flow capacity, further intensifying the Spillage. Starting from the time marked by the red dashed line, the Spillage begins to increase rapidly. The strengthened Spillage further enhances the SPV intensity in adjacent passages. This mutual reinforcement is intensified by the feedback between neighboring passages, which eventually induces a tornado-like vortex at the leading edge and resulting in the stall of BS.

FIGURE 10: THROTTLING PROCESS OF BLOCAKGE AND SPIILAGE AND TYPICAL INSTANTANEOUS VORTES CORE DISTRIBUTION ($Q = 1.06 \times 10^6$)

As shown in Figure 10, the Blockage within the blade passage exhibits periodic fluctuations. Figure 11 presents the evolution of the periodic average Blockage during the throttling process, with the blue dashed line indicating the onset of its

continuous increase. As previously analyzed, the extension of SPV across the passage marks the onset of the BS stall, corresponding to a periodic average blockage coefficient of approximately 5.37. Furthermore, DMD analysis of the flow field at $\varphi = 0.2050$ shows that the f_g of SPV is 0.701 BPF, and f_s is 0.500 BPF; whereas at $\varphi = 0.1981$, the f_g of SPV decreases to 0.679 BPF, while f_s remains at 0.500 BPF. This trend indicates that as throttling, the volume of SPV increases, and its corresponding generation frequency decreases.

FIGURE 11: EVOLUTION OF THE PERIODIC-AVERAGED BLOCAGE AT $0.5C_{ax}$ DURING THE THROTTLING PROCESS

In summary, under near-stall conditions, the primary flow feature of BS tip region is the generation and shedding of the SPV. As throttling, the SPV continuously strengthens, accompanied by a decrease in its generation frequency. The stall onset of BS is characterized by a sustained and rapid increase in passage blockage, triggered by the SPV extending across the blade passage. Suppressing this phenomenon could lead to improvements in flow stability.

3.3 Shared features in stability improvement by steady and unsteady micro tip injection

Although uniform and unsteady micro tip injections differ in excitation form and the resulting mechanisms of stability improvement, they exhibit comparable features in enhancing stability. This subsection discusses the stall margin improvement mechanism of UI injection and the shared features underlying both schemes.

The injection location for both cases is positioned at $0.5C_{ax}$ downstream of the rotor blade tip leading edge. The BPFi injection alternates between two nozzles, but the number of excitation present in the flow field at any given time is the same as in the UI case. As a result, both injection schemes introduce similar pressure disturbances into the flow field. Figure 12(1) shows the distribution of static pressure coefficient C_{ps} at 0.99 blade height under stable injection and during the pulsating moment. The injection induces a pair of high-pressure and low-pressure regions at stable condition. When pulsating, a low-pressure zone is generated at the previous injection site, and this disturbance dissipates within two time steps. Figure 12(2) compares the tip leakage velocity distributions of R1 at $0.5C_{ax}$ between the baseline case (BS) and the two excitation cases, with the velocity normalized by the mid-span circumferential velocity of the rotor blade. Both BPFi and UI injections modify the tip blade loading through local pressure disturbances, thereby enhancing the mid-chord tip leakage flow. Compared to

UI injection, the alternating nature of BPFi injection further changes the timing of leakage enhancement. In addition, the introduction of micro tip injection alters the wall boundary condition, due to its relative motion with respect to the rotor flow field, generates a wall shear directed toward the pressure side of the blade.

(1) THE EFFECT OF INJECTION ON C_{ps} DISTRIBUTION

(2) THE EFFECT OF INJECTIONS ON TIP LEAKAGE FLOW ($0.5C_{ax}$)

FIGURE 12: $\varphi = 0.1981$, THE C_{ps} DISTRIBUTION AT 0.99 SPANWISE LOCATION AND THE NORMALIZED TIP LEAKAGE VELOCITY AT $0.5 C_{ax}$ AFTER MICRO TIP INJECTION EVOLUTION OF THE PERIODIC-AVERAGED BLOCAGE AT $0.5C_{ax}$ DURING THE THROTTLING PROCESS

Under the BPFi and UI injection, the main feature of the near-stall tip flow field remains the periodic generation and shedding of SPV. The injections enhance the mid-chord leakage flow and wall shear effects, promoting circumferential migration of the tip fluid. On the one hand, the strengthened leakage flow guides the fluid inside the SPV into adjacent blade passages, thereby weakening its strength; on the other hand, wall shear and circumferential migration stretch the SPV toward the pressure side of the passage, resulting in dissipation. The combined effects contribute to the attenuation of SPV strength. Figure 13 presents $\varphi = 0.1981$, the fluctuation of Blockage at $0.5 C_{ax}$, corresponding to the flow condition in Figure 8(2), under conditions with and without injection. As the primary flow structure within the passage, SPV is the main source of Blockage fluctuations. Both types of jet excitation reduce the Blockage in the passage, indicating their effective suppression of the SPV.

FIGURE 13: COMPARISON OF INSTANTANEOUS BLOCKAGE AFTER BPF AND UI INJECTION AT $\varphi = 0.1981$

Figure 14(1) compares the generation frequency f_g and shedding frequency f_s of the SPV under conditions with and without injection. Both BPF and UI micro tip injections increase f_g but do not alter f_s . The f_g after BPF injection is 0.688BPF, and the f_g after UI injection is 0.687BPF. According to previous analysis, a decrease in f_g is associated with SPV intensification; therefore, the observed frequency increase further indicates that both UI and BPF injection weakens the SPV. Taking 22/30T marked by the black dashed line in Figure 13 as an example, Figure 14(2) illustrates the vortex core distribution identified by the Q-criterion and the reconstructed flow field of f_g with and without excitation. Compared to BS, SPV size is reduced under both unsteady and uniform excitation. Moreover, f_g disturbance intensity decreases, further confirming the effectiveness of jet excitation in suppressing SPV development.

(1)VARIATION OF SPV CHARACTERISTIC FREQUENCY AFTER UI AND BPF INJECTIONS

(2)VORTEX CORE DISTRIBUTION AND DMD RECONSTRUCTED FLOW FIELD AT 22/30T ($Q = 1.06 \times 10^6$)

FIGURE 14: EFFECTS OF UI AND BPF INJECTIONS ON SPV

Under the flow coefficient ($\varphi = 0.1981$) corresponding to the stable boundary of BS, an increase of 2 Pa in outlet static pressure leads the flow toward stall, whereas the application of UI and BPF micro injections delays the onset of this phenomenon. Figure 15 presents the distribution of the periodic-averaged Blockage of $0.5 C_{ax}$ before and after throttling under UI and BPF injections. Although throttling increases Blockage within the passage, Blockage under both injections remain below the critical value of 5.37 corresponding to SPV across the passage, which is the main cause of stall onset, and the flow remains stable.

(1)UNDER UI MICRO TIP INJECTION

(2)UNDER BPF MICRO TIP INJECTION

FIGURE 15: VARIATION OF PERIODIC-AVERAGED BLOCKAGE AT $0.5 C_{ax}$ UNDER UI AND BPFI MICRO TIP INJECTIONS

In summary, the stall margin improvement of UI injection arises from its ability to introduce local pressure fluctuations, enhance mid-chord leakage flow, and strengthen wall shear, thereby suppressing the development of the key flow structure (SPV) within the passage and broadening the stability boundary. Although BPFI alters the distribution of mid-chord leakage, it produces a similar effect, indicating a shared mechanism between the two injection schemes.

3.4 Different mechanism of stability improvement by unsteady and uniform micro tip injection

The distinct mechanism of stability improvement observed in unsteady micro tip injection stems from its pulsating characteristics. This section will focus on how these unsteady features alter the stability mechanism compared with uniform injection.

As shown in Fig 12, compared to UI injection, BPFI injection alters the temporal distribution of leakage flow enhancement due to its pulsating characteristics. Figure 16 compares the periodic-averaged fluctuations of leakage velocity under UI and BPFI injections at a same flow coefficient, with black dashed lines indicating the average leakage flow over one rotor revolution for each case. The flow condition $\varphi = 0.1967$ correspond to the stability boundary under UI injection. Over a longer time scale, for example within one rotor revolution, the overall intensity of leakage flow by UI and BPFI injections is generally similar. However, due to its pulsating nature, BPFI injection concentrates the leakage flow enhancement, thereby increasing the fluctuation intensity of leakage flow in a periodic-averaged sense.

FIGURE 16: PERIODIC-AVERAGED FLUCTUATIONS OF LEAKAGE VELOCITY UNDER UI AND BPFI INJECTIONS AT VARIATION OF PERIODIC-AVERAGED BLOCKAGE AT $\varphi = 0.1967$

Figure 17 compares the DMD-reconstructed flow fields corresponding to the SPV shedding frequency within one cycle

under UI and BPFI injections, with flow conditions consistent with those in Figure 8. Under UI injection, the reconstructed flow evolution closely resembles that of the baseline case, showing only a slight attenuation in fluctuation amplitude. In contrast, BPFI injection introduces an additional circumferential mode propagating toward the blade pressure surface. This indicates that the pulsation induced by BPFI, due to its alternating nature, not only matches the SPV shedding frequency but also actively promotes the propagation of the shedding disturbance toward the pressure surface.

FIGURE 17: THE DMD RECONSTRUCTED FLOW FIELD OF SPV SHEDDING FREQUENCY UNDER UI AND BPFI MICRO TIP INJECTIONS

Compared to UI micro tip injection, BPFI micro tip injection results in a more concentrated enhancement of the leakage flow and more pronounced fluctuations in leakage flow intensity. Figure 18 illustrates the temporal evolution of the period-averaged Blockage at the $0.5 C_{ax}$ under both UI and BPFI injections, at stable boundaries and during stall processes. The flow coefficients corresponding to the stable boundary of UI injection and BPFI injection are $\varphi = 0.1967$ and $\varphi = 0.1955$. Since BPFI injection concentrates the leakage distribution and increase the leakage fluctuation intensity in a periodic-averaged sense. When the leakage flow intensity reaches its peak, it accelerates the movement of fluid within the SPV into the adjacent blade passage through the tip clearance, thereby weakening the SPV. At the same time, it promotes the circumferential migration of fluid along the suction side, suppressing the development of the SPV across the passage. Conversely, when the leakage flow intensity is at a trough, its suppression effect on the SPV diminishes. The SPV continues to expand within the passage, but it still does not develop across the passage. Moreover, its intensification cannot be sustained and is suppressed again in the next fluctuation cycle, preventing any feedback-induced amplification. As a result, in

terms of the period-averaged Blockage of the stability boundaries, BPFJ injection maintains a higher yet stable Blockage level within the passage without progressing toward instability, thereby further extending the stability boundary. However, even with the application of UI and BPFJ micro injections, the onset of stall in this low-speed compressor is still marked by the SPV developing across the blade passage. This phenomenon corresponds to a critical passage blockage coefficient of 5.37, which is consistent with the stall onset observed under the baseline condition. The red dashed line in the figure indicates this critical blockage coefficient.

FIGURE 18: EVOLUTION OF THE PERIODIC-AVERAGED BLOCAGE AT $0.5 C_{ax}$ AT THE STABLE BOUNDARIES AND DURING THE THROTTLING PROCESS UNDER UI AND BPFJ INJECTIONS

In summary, the key difference between BPFJ and UI injections in stability enhancement mechanisms lies in the dynamic fluctuation characteristics of the mid-chord leakage flow intensity. Due to its alternating nature, BPFJ injection leads to more concentrated leakage flow enhancement and amplifies the fluctuation amplitude of the period-averaged leakage intensity. This dynamically strengthens the suppression of the SPV intensity and its tendency to develop across the blade passage, thereby preventing sustained expansion and feedback reinforcement of the SPV within the passage, ultimately further improved compressor stability.

4. CONCLUSION

A comparative investigation is conducted into the effects of unsteady (BPFJ) and uniform (UI) micro tip injection on the stability enhancement of a low-speed axial compressor. The key findings are summarized as follows:

Stall onset in the investigated compressor is initiated by the SPV developing across the blade passage, and resulting from its inter-passage feedback reinforcement.

Both BPFJ and UI micro tip injections extend the compressor's stall margin with negligible effect on radial blade load distribution. BPFJ injection achieves 1.31% stall margin improvement and UI injection achieves 0.71%.

The stability improvement mechanism of UI injection lies in its ability to enhance mid-chord leakage flow and wall shear, thereby suppressing SPV development within the passage and delay stall onset. This mechanism is shared by both UI and BPFJ, while neither alters the critical blockage coefficient corresponding to stall onset.

The different mechanism of stability improvement by

unsteady micro tip injection arises from its alternating character. In contrast to uniform injection, it induces concentrated leakage enhancement and pronounced fluctuations in the period-averaged leakage intensity, leading to dynamic suppression of SPV development and interruption of the feedback loop, and thus achieves a distinct improvement in compressor stability.

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